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Bibliometric Analysis: Symbolic Power Publication Trends in Scopus.com

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to explore references to one source that can provide benefits for researchers about symbolic power, it is in the interest to use bibliometric methods to map the specification of research, namely 1) to reveal the number of articles produced by symbolic power research. 2) Conduct mapping to review symbolic power research that has been done, and 3) reveal the collaboration map. The method provides objective parameters in controlling literature and provides opportunities to encourage increased accuracy and minimize the bias of researchers in scientific literature reviews by paying attention to the research results of scholars working in the field research area. This bibliometric method provided citation analysis guidelines, co-citation analysis, coupling bibliography, co-author analysis, and co-word analysis, as well as work guidelines. Bibliometric methods would complement the meta-analysis and review of qualitatively structured literature as a method for exploring and evaluating scientific literature. To demonstrate bibliometric methods, it was done with citation analysis and co-citation to map the intellectual structure of symbolic power journals. The results showed that the investigation of human-related symbolic power was shown by 109 events widely published by the scopus.com database during 2012-2022. From the mapping carried out through bibliometrics shows that the trend of research is related to the term human keywords.

Keywords: Bibliometric, Publication, Research Development, Symbolic Power

1. Introduction

Two concepts of political sociology and Bourdieu legitimacy as the production of power. This power cannot be separated from the practice of violence through the repressive state apparatus and symbolic violence created in civil society ideologically (Sullivan et al., 2019). Symbolic power is the choice of meaning produced by the agent's ego (Bergström et al., 2019). This symbolic power is a subtle practice of domination and is not even realized by social agents. But it is also maintained and accepted rationally (Molla, 2019). The development of research on symbolic power is widely done in relation to gender, social class, religion. Women's protection reasoning becomes a reference to gender attributes (Johnson, 2017). The social structure and involvement of women in a variety of ways, especially their role in the economy can overcome marginalization and even violence against women. The same social interactions can lead to changes in mindset, attitudes and social practices (Bradley et al., 2021). Mobility is also determined by material forces in the relationship of social processes and cultural, political, social, economic (Dunne et al., 2020; Grieco, 2016).

Social class is part of the social structure that determines the change of society. Certain social classes can be recognized through symbols, such as home appearance, means of transportation, how to dress, and social relationships (Mere & Ngarawula, 2015). Social space as a public domain, used as actualization to gain the social position of the agent and its success (Hjellbrekke & Korsnes, 2017). Success in its social position is a form of struggle to stay in power, influence, and control environmental change (Fernández, 2013; Gadea, 2013; Zapata & Romero, 2019). Religion is one of the social structures that influence the way religious practices. Religious practices in society carried out by its adherents often give birth to symbolic violence. The excessive behavior of individuals and social groups can sometimes be influenced by their religious experiences. For example, Islam as a religion forbids going beyond all the practices of life in various fields (Ramlee et al., 2019). Such as: the position of women in the patriarchy system is placed in other positions or subordinated as evidenced by the practice of women/wives' obedience in their religious beliefs towards their husbands (Nurmila, 2018). Therefore, the social representation of women and men's positions is largely determined by the mastery of capital as a form of dominance over women (Campos & Lima, 2018; Perrin et al., 2019).

Bourdieu is a figure who developed the concept of symbolic power supported by the concept of mastery of various capitals. This mastery of capital aims to obtain a certain agent's social position. The importance of harnessing the potential between significant capital and differences in social space (Pöllmann, 2013). The utilization of communication media with the largest platform is the practice of symbolic power (Ranji, 2021). Big data provides an overview of the sources of science, creativity, innovative ideas, and the tendency to change improvement and development. In context, the interpretation of digitalization artifacts is an asiosative reflection of the social space and competition scene (Macfarlane & Jefferson, 2022). The tendency to practice symbolic power through mastery of social, cultural, and political capital in a college environment often contrasts with the career needs of academics. Paradoxically this is an unavoidable form of competition (Ku, 2004; Stringfellow et al., 2015).

However, research on the topic of symbolic power using bibliometric methods has not been done so that no published articles have been found. Some research on symbolic power uses ethnographic methods, surveys, time series, regression analysis, and formal analysis (Golonka-Czajkowska, 2019; Morello SJ, 2019; Sikevich & Skvortsov, 2020; Woodfill, 2021). Open and critical attitude as one of the signs of modernity. But there is a tendency for progress and damage to be opened up to visualize positive and negative impacts (Barash & Antonovskiy, 2019). Open access to mapping specific social phenomena or problems, focuses on comparing and at the same time developing the results of existing and still little-studied research (Pearce et al., 2020). The novelty of this study uses bibliometric methods, and is also used for the study of search attraction (Chen & Song, 2019) corporate social responsibility and progress for survival, as well as future trends (Abad-Segura et al., 2019; Tayebi et al., 2019; Williams, 2020). In addition, other fields such as economics and econometrics are analyzed and published by individuals as academics in their research environment (Chan et al., 2015; Kauppi, 2018). Based on the growing research, the author aims to explore how much the development of international articles with symbolic topics of power from 2013 to 2022. The problem in these studies are (1) How is the trend of publishing articles about symbolic power, (2) How the author cooperates on symbolic power in 2013-2022. (3) What is the trendy keyword term author in the symbolic article of power, (4) How the abstract term trend in the article symbolic power.

2. Material and Method

Bibliometric methods were used in this study. The data source used was sourced on the www.scopus.com. The technique of collecting data by tracing the scopus. The data was then bibliometrically analyzed. The steps were as follows: search stage, filterization stage, bibliometric attribute review, and bibliometric analysis.

2.1. Search Stage

Bibliographies are used for database searches in scopus. The use of scopus database sources was a top choice, as it is one of the largest databases by providing peer-reviewed literature and publications. This study was limited by several aspects. First, the types of sources used in scopus were journal articles, abstarck, and keywords. Second,

keywords used were symbolic power. Third, the use of English in the article as a restriction.

2.2. Filtering Stage

Filtering is used for the selection of journals to be analyzed. Bibliography options were article titles, abstracts, keywords, articles, or reviews. The initial stage in the search through scopus found 4970 articles through searches restricted to the keyword "symbolic power." and screening of the title of the article in English. In addition, for 10 years starting in 1013-2022 and in each year experiencing fluctuating, high publications in 2021 and in 2022 the trend decreased, such as table.1 below:

Table 1: Filtered Document Period.

Mapping the subject area was also done to find out quantitatively the theme of symbolic power in the data scopus.com. In this case, the number of articles that correlate in each subect area, including: social sciences, art and Humanities, mathematics, computer science, engineering, environmental science, medicine, business, management and accounting, and economic, psychology, and physics and astronomy. as in table.2 Subject Area. The highest symbolic power publication in the field of social science reached 884 articles, while the lowest in the field of physics and astronomy reached 61 articles as in table 2 below:

Table 2: Subject Area

The next step was to choose the creating menu. Then select creating a map base on bibliographic database file (input files that have been extracted from scopus in ris form. Click next, then select co-occurrence -co authorship/co citation, click next, click finish.

2.3. *Stage of Bibliometric Analysis*

This stage of bibliometric analysis is to provide a quantitative overview of the development of social and network studies. In addition, to map the position of the topic. In addition, identification can also be carried out relevance of the level of interaction and its influence on the sample (Machado et al., 2020; Tayebi et al., 2019). The Vos viewer application was used to visualize its analyst results. In addition, text-mining was used to describe relationships in article citations. Systemic data processing via computerization contributes to analyzing article trends in a journal and periodical international publications.

The data obtained from the above filtering is entered for analysis through the Vos viewer. The number of choices from keywords obtained every 692 keywords, the amount of power of co-occurrence links with other keywords can be calculated. The result was that the keywords with the largest total strength associated would be selected with a number of other key words selected to 692.

3. Results and Discussion

The visualization of this article is based on Vos's viewer application to map the tendency of symbolic power studies and link with other variables. Network visualization, overlay visualization and density visualization were developed by researchers in the last 10 years from 2013-2022. Based on the choice of data type in the scopus.com about symbolic power by making a mapping on the bibliometric data available. The author chooses this mapping for the type of analysis co-authorship and the unit is the author. While counting method with full counting. The result is a maximum number of authors per document of 25. Analysis of co-occurrence and keywords in full counting resulted in a minimum number of occurrences of a keyword amounting to 3 of the 8089 keywords, 692 meet the threshold. In terms of choosing number of keywords for each of the 692 keywords, the total strength of the co-occurrence links with other keywords will be calculated. The keywords with the greatest total link strength will be selected. Number of keywords to be selected 692 items. Obtained 9 clusters with details of clusters 1 (238), clusters 2 (214 items), cluster 3 (82 items), cluster 4 (51 items), cluster 5 (37 items), cluster 6 (35 items), cluster 7 (22 items), cluster 8 (11 items), and cluster 9 (2 items). In relation to cluster 9, the publication of his research related to beliefs and the Netherlands as the smallest cluster.

3.1 *Network Visualization: Symbolic Publication Trends and Authors Network*

Based on the figure 3., image provides information that the direction of the tendency of the study of symbolic power is related to 9 clusters. Based on gb 3, on symbolic power obtained cluster 6, 116 links, total link strength 195, and 80 occurrences. But in the same cluster of symbolic powers items in the form of plural there are differences in the number such as, obtained 34 links, total link strength 92, and 49 occurrences. In this symbolic power study, the most related to the term "human" amounted to 361 links, its position in cluster 3 with the number of link strengths as many as 1389 and 109 events.

Bourdieu cluster 1 items have 129 links and total link strengths of 231 and 52 occurrences. Studies developed related to theory symbolic power related to gender, violence, have been widely done, but related to human and controlled studies there are still very few publications.

Figure 3: Symbolic power Network Visualization

Figure 4. Visualization of author network after choosing threshold with number of documents of an author 3 of the 2807 author, 62 meet the threshold. For each of the 62 authors, the total strength of the co-authorship links with other authors will be calculated. The authors with the greatest total link strength will be selected. Number of authors to be selected 62. Some of the 36 items in this network are not connected to each other. The largest set of connected items consists of 22 items with (5 clusters). Cluster 1 (7 items), cluster 2 (6 items), cluster 3 (4 items), cluster 4 (3 items), cluster 5 (2 items). Author Drabkin, b only related to Seceleanu, a. both are authors who have the smallest link. Meanwhile, the author who has the largest link is Bocci, c as many as 6 links.

Figure 4: Author network visualization

3.2 Visualization overlay: Visualization trends

The label display is very useful for detailed examination of the map. In this visualization, it is displayed with clear and obscure labels, as well as circles. The clearer and greater the visualization, the more studies that have been done by the authors. Overlap can be avoided, the emergence of a subset of all labels.

Figure 5: Overlay visualization

3.3 Density visualization

Collaborative research cooperation can build the power of providing research funds and providing mutualistic benefits in the form of: data, skill ideas and infrastructure. Improving the quality of research and ideals at the international level can be achieved more effectively.

Figure 6: Visualization of density symbolic power

Symbolic power article data is searched through the international database scopus.com. From the search results, journal articles that have been collected and limited for the period 2013-2022 with all open acces journals and gold and hybridgold levels, are 1685 articles. As for the details of the search results in table 1. Furthermore, in the search of the subject area obtained the results from 10 scientific fields, as in table 2. In the table obtained the highest social science results in discussions related to symbolic power as many as 884 articles, the field of art and humanities second with the number of 487 articles, and the lowest order in physics and astronomy amounting to 61 articles.

On figure 5. The term human has a lot to do with symbolic power research and has the most links of 1389 in 109 events. Human is included in cluster 3 and there is information that the study is related to architectural design as the highest term, the 2nd rank is attitude of personal health, and the 3rd rank is behavior. The use of algorithms was developed and became a more advanced trend through architectural design in many scientific arenas regarding symbolic power (Bai et al., 2022). The study of onshore wind turbines against the wind that serves for tower congestion, the utilization of these turbines for the fulfillment of human needs (Ning & Petch, 2016). Methodology review is used by practitioners to develop prototypes sourced from commercial sensors and used to reduce costs (Demirel et al., 2021; Pérez-Valero et al., 2020). The internet network is designed as a communication medium providing a space for protest and conflict (Barash & Antonovskiy, 2019).

The term attitude of personal health is a personal view related to efforts to avoid various diseases. The extent to which the direction of development is related to symbolic power. The number of links owned is as many as 60 in 3 events. Symbolic material about social practices, especially relationships with nurses and hypertensive people develops asymmetrically (Borges et al., 2012). Symbolism is used as one of the analysis related to distribution and prevention in society (Caprara, 1998). Similar research, Public perception of clean hydropower infrastructure services and environmental protection of coal mining is related to people's helplessness over aesthetic symbolic eating, the environment, and tourism (Dubois et al., 2021). Research aims to explore multi-component interventions on risk behaviors, smoking, eating, exercise affecting health (Mikkelsen et al., 2021). The symbolic power of the patient and the public with respect to the power of the capitals owned by the patient (Locock et al., 2017). Nursing position with the study of the interconnection of political interests, knowledge of laws relating to gender sensitivity (Trisyani & Windsor, 2019).

Publication based on the term behavior with symbolic power links linked to 119 articles in 8 events, indicated by the researchers as follows; The strength of the actor in the implementation of the work program is determined by the symbolic power of religiosity integrated in the organizational system (Biygautane et al., 2020). The development of political career leadership theory and capital accumulation strategies is related to ideological and charismatic leadership (Mendes, 2021). Women's beauty symbols are exploited by the media and the advantages of global consumerism (Xu, 2019). Symbolic violence for university research careers occurred and mediated the market, performative, and managerial various modern neoliberal universities. (Gordon & Zainuddin, 2020). Research development directions were developed as well, such as: The use of perfectoid algebra with mixed analog characteristics over ordinary ambient ring cases (Ma & Schwede, 2018). The motivational aspect is an influential aspect for policymakers over independent authority (Lombardi & Moschella, 2017). The social position of agents on the mastery of economic capital accumulates higher and is not clearly defined with regard to economic status and access to resources (Veenstra, 2018).

The publication of research on symbolic power linked to other keywords amounted to 195 links and 80 occurrences. As for the direction of development of its publication, as follows: The power of symbols is awakened through the interaction and intensity of social collective actions (Schlieter, 2017). Heterosexual spaces and cultural differences give birth to changes in mobility to meet rights and obligations, as well as public policy support (Đurin, 2018). Social space is correlated with the power relations and social classes of thought of Foucault, Gramsci, Bourdieu, and Marx. used to express the life experiences of parents as they interact with food policy, rejection of stigmatization; and implications for policy and practice (Noonan-Gunning, 2019). The fear and violence experienced by women symbolized in the mobilization of marches as social spaces, is a criticism of society's inability to solve problems of gender relations and limited access (Sandberg & Coe, 2020). Research on the interaction of many young people's drinking habits and exercise and their implications, social and physical health is produced by the dominance of masculine (Cowley, 2019; Törrönen et al., 2021). The study of epistemological vigilance was developed by researchers related to symbolic power. Dialectics of symbolic, social, material and social structures (Wacquant, 2017, 2018). Different research on whether FC-metric weighted Phase Lag Index (wPLI) and Symbolic Mutual Information (wSMI) for analysis of functional differences in four stages of alertness - awake (W), NREM-N2, NREM-N3, and REM sleep - relation to each other and power-based features (Imperator et al., 2021). Symbolic entities are studied in terms of life, culture, psychological on the realities of life (Cowley, 2019). The use of protest symbols in the form of slogans requires understanding and thinking power over

the guarantee of transparency of protest functions (Barash & Antonovskiy, 2019). In addition, fatpoint is related to the concept of symbolic power regarding the study of generic early systems and lexicography (Mayes, 2016).

Publications of research on resurgen developed by researchers include, symbolic power and power of algebraic interests give symbolically for the benefit of students (Dumnicki et al., 2015). Likewise, The study of the superiority of coata on the functional and symbolic significance of the castle town in Burwel (Wright et al., 2016). Study of network nodes with symbolic implementation and combined with window detection techniques (Zeng et al., 2017), A study of symbolic power about the chaos of clicks on deep graphs and the similarity of results over the same ideal cover (Martínez-Bernal et al., 2019). Social change and the scope of modernity are studied through a symbolic hermeneutic approach to the field (Kokosalakis, 2020). In a different approach, such as ethnographic studies of ritual practices on the theme of the film world as a way religious categories are conceptualized (Moran, 2021). The attitude of responsibility, resilience, and symbolic power is a reciprocal nature relationship in building a community collective (King et al., 2021).

4. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussions, it can be concluded that publications about symbolic power during the period 2013-20222 showed that the highest Scopus index of symbolic power publications in the field of social science reached 884 articles. The highest increase occurred in 2021. Bocci, c is the researcher who has the highest links. In the analysis of title trends, 9 clusters were formed. The most widely used term title in symbolic power articles is related to humans with 109 events. The authors suggest the need to add new keywords to get more research results so that they are more comprehensive. In terms of limitations this study has not revealed the mapping methods used in the research published by researchers in the period 2013-2022.

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